

RIS-Aided NLoS Monostatic Multi-Target Sensing under Angle-Doppler Coupling

Mahmut Kemal Ercan, *Student Member, IEEE*, Alireza Pourafzal, *Member, IEEE*,
Musa Furkan Keskin, *Member, IEEE*, Sinan Gezici, *Senior Member, IEEE*, and Henk Wymeersch, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—We investigate the problem of reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS)-aided monostatic sensing of multiple mobile targets under line-of-sight (LoS) blockage using a dual-functional radar-communications base station. For the purpose of target detection and delay/Doppler/angle estimation, we derive a detector based on the generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT), which entails a high-dimensional parameter search with high complexity due to angle-Doppler coupling. To circumvent the coupling effect, we introduce a repetitive RIS phase profile design accompanied by a multi-target detection/estimation algorithm based on orthogonal matching pursuit where each iteration solves the single-target GLRT problem and outputs the corresponding parameter estimates. Moreover, as a low-complexity alternative, we introduce a novel subspace-based algorithm based on two-dimensional unitary ESPRIT to retrieve target parameters in a non-iterative manner. Simulation results verify the effectiveness of the proposed algorithms, demonstrating their convergence to theoretical bounds and revealing significant improvements over state-of-the-art benchmarks in complexity and performance.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS), monostatic sensing, non-line-of-sight (NLoS) sensing, angle-Doppler coupling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) are emerging as a key technology for 6G, offering the potential to significantly enhance communication rates and coverage by overcoming signal blockages, especially in mmWave and sub-THz systems [1]–[3]. In addition to improving communication, RISs can also enhance sensing capabilities, enabling integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) [4], [5], [6]. Applications include monostatic [7], bistatic [8] and multistatic [9] sensing, as well as simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [10]. RIS-aided sensing offers several advantages over traditional sensing without RIS, such as RIS phase profile design for specific sector illumination [11], [12], non-line-of-sight (NLoS) sensing in the presence of obstacles [13]–[15], improving signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [16] and providing high-accuracy angle estimation via large aperture of RIS [17].

In RIS-aided sensing, monostatic setups have been widely studied [8], [13], [15], [18]–[23], particularly due to their attractive properties, including ease of synchronization and utilization of the entire signal (i.e., not only pilots). When

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Mahmut Kemal Ercan and Sinan Gezici are with the Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Bilkent University, 06800 Ankara, Turkey (e-mail: ercan@ee.bilkent.edu.tr; gezici@ee.bilkent.edu.tr).

Alireza Pourafzal, Musa Furkan Keskin, and Henk Wymeersch are with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology, 412 96 Göteborg, Sweden (e-mail: alireza.pourafzal@chalmers.se; furkan@chalmers.se; henkw@chalmers.se).

Fig. 1. RIS-aided monostatic sensing scenario under LoS blockage. A BS detects mobile targets using the backscattered signals over the RIS path by using the pilot signals. These pilots are also used by the user equipments (UEs) to localize themselves, avoiding subsequent beam pairing for communication.

the line-of-sight (LoS) path exists between the monostatic radar transceiver and the target, RIS can enhance the SNR by introducing an additional, controllable path towards the target through judicious design of RIS element phases [16], [21]. Under LoS blockage conditions (as shown in Fig. 1), RIS can act as an additional anchor to provide high-resolution angle-of-departure (AoD) or angle-of-arrival (AoA) measurements of potential targets [13]. By using sufficient bandwidth, such as with orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) transmissions [24], [25], the monostatic radar can combine angular information with round-trip delay measurements over the RIS-induced NLoS path to perform high-accuracy localization of targets in a surveillance area blocked by obstacles [15].

A key challenge in RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing lies in detection and parameter estimation of *mobile targets*. Specifically, target angle information can only be obtained via the RIS, which, due to its passive nature (i.e., lacking a sampling mechanism), causes beamspace measurements at the radar receiver and requires multiple non-parallel RIS configurations. Simultaneously, target Doppler is estimated through slow-time phase shifts across transmissions. Hence, the impact of mobility and RIS beam sweeping on slow-time phase shifts cannot be disentangled from each other, leading to the *angle-Doppler coupling* effect [26]. While a few studies have explored RIS-aided sensing of mobile targets [14], [15], [20], [24], [25], these primarily focus on RIS phase profile optimization and waveform design, often omitting the detailed algorithmic aspects necessary for addressing such complexities.

The algorithmic challenges of angle-Doppler coupling re-

ceive attention in [27], [28] and [29]. For instance, in [27], a two-stage approach is adopted where coarse-grained sensing using hierarchical 3D RIS beamforming initially detects targets and their directions (i.e., AoDs). Then, during fine-grained sensing, RIS beams are directed towards the detected targets to estimate their ranges and velocities. Similarly, the methodology proposed in [28] focuses on estimating the delay, Doppler and angle parameters of mobile targets, performing detection and range-Doppler processing per directional RIS beam, which necessitates parameter pairing across all RIS configurations and is inherently sub-optimal. Meanwhile, [29] introduces a low-complexity method that decomposes the observed signal into range, Doppler and angle dimensions, and then employs a one-dimensional search to extract range and Doppler information, followed by a two-dimensional search to determine angles. This approach leverages higher-order singular value decomposition (SVD) for decomposing the observed signal tensor, again requiring parameter pairing in multi-target scenarios. In summary, the effectiveness of [27] heavily depends on the robustness of the initial target detection, which could be challenging in the presence of multiple targets due to side-lobe interference. Moreover, [28] and [29] are limited by the necessity for *multi-target parameter pairing*, which would constitute a significant shortcoming in practical scenarios. In light of the existing literature, the two compelling problems remain unanswered in RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing: (i) how to perform low-complexity coherent processing over all measurements for detection and four-dimensional (range-Doppler-azimuth-elevation) estimation of *multiple mobile targets*, and (ii) how to solve the accompanying problem of angle-Doppler coupling.

Starting from our preliminary analysis in [30], we fill this gap by tackling the problem of RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing of multiple mobile targets using the echoes of downlink signals transmitted by a dual-functional ISAC BS, coherently processing all observations for arbitrary RIS configurations. Our specific contributions are as follows:

- **Generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT) detector for mobile targets:** We derive the GLRT detector, which involves computationally complex four-dimensional parameter search over range-Doppler-azimuth-elevation domains due to angle-Doppler coupling inherent to RIS-aided angle estimation under mobility.
- **RIS phase profile design and single-target estimator:** To address the computational complexity challenge, we propose repetitive RIS phase profiles and devise a novel GLRT-based detector/estimator that exploits the proposed temporal design to circumvent the angle-Doppler coupling effect, enabling separate estimation of delay-Doppler and azimuth-elevation.
- **Multi-target detection/estimation via orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) and unitary ESPRIT:** We develop two methods for multi-target detection and estimation. The first method is based on OMP with successive interference cancellation, whereby the single-target GLRT-based estimator is employed at each iteration to obtain parameter estimates of the current strongest target. The second method provides a low-complexity, non-iterative alternative to the first one, leveraging a subspace-based approach via two-

dimensional unitary ESPRIT, which estimates target parameters by decomposing the signal matrix into range, Doppler and angular domains. Unlike [28] and [29], neither of the proposed methods requires parameter pairing across multiple targets.

Additionally, simulation results reveal the effectiveness of the proposed phase profile design and methods in mobile target sensing, showing significant improvements in complexity and performance over state-of-the-art benchmarks.

Notation: We use upper-case and lower-case boldface letters to denote matrices and vectors, respectively. $[\cdot]_i$ denotes the i th element of a vector, $[\cdot]_{i,j}$ denotes the element in the i th row and j th column, and $:$ denotes all the elements in the row/column. We also denote transpose, Hermitian, and complex conjugate by $(\cdot)^T$, $(\cdot)^H$, and $(\cdot)^*$, respectively. In addition, $\|\cdot\|$, $\|\cdot\|_F$, $\text{diag}(\cdot)$, and $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ denotes the ℓ_2 norm, Frobenius norm, diagonal, and trace operations, respectively. The Hadamard and Kronecker products are denoted by \odot and \otimes , respectively. The complex set with $N \times M$ dimensions is denoted by $\mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$. For scalars, $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute value (or, magnitude of a complex number).

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we describe the RIS-aided NLoS sensing scenario, derive the signal model at the BS, and formulate the problem of detection/estimation of a mobile target.

A. Scenario

We consider the RIS-aided monostatic sensing scenario under LoS blockage as shown in Fig. 1, where a full-duplex dual-functional radar-communications base station with a known location performs monostatic sensing using the echoes of downlink (DL) transmissions through the RIS-induced NLoS path [31], [32]. The aim is to detect multiple mobile targets in the environment and estimate their parameters (delay, Doppler, angle). The base station is equipped with a single transmit (TX) and a single receive (RX) antenna, while the RIS has N_{RIS} elements. In addition, the RIS is assumed to have a known location and orientation.

B. Signal Model

For DL communications with a UE, the BS transmits an OFDM signal with N subcarriers and M symbols¹, with $x_{n,m}$ denoting the complex data/pilot on the n^{th} subcarrier of the m^{th} symbol. The subcarrier spacing and the symbol duration are defined as $\Delta_f = 1/T$ and $T_s = T + T_{\text{CP}}$, respectively, with T denoting the elementary symbol duration and T_{CP} the cyclic prefix (CP) duration. We assume the existence of K targets in the environment characterized by states $\{\alpha_k, \tau_k, \nu_k, \theta_k\}$, which will be defined shortly. To prevent intersymbol interference (ISI), the CP duration is assumed to be larger than the round-trip delay of the target over the RIS path [33]–[36]. In this setup, the backscattered OFDM signal at the monostatic sensing receiver of the BS on the n^{th} subcarrier of the m^{th}

¹Our design utilizes full pilot sample allocation across subcarriers, diverging from typical pilot sequences (sparsely scattered in the frequency-time plane) employed in standard systems. This approach can be considered as initiating a beam sweeping phase, where the system directs beams in various directions to comprehensively map the environment, identify the most effective communication paths and locate targets within the coverage area.

symbol (after removing the CP and switching to frequency-domain) can be written as [13], [14], [30]

$$y_{n,m} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k (\mathbf{a}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \boldsymbol{\Omega}_m \mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}}))^2 [\mathbf{c}(\tau_k)]_n [\mathbf{d}(\nu_k)]_m x_{n,m} + z_{n,m}, \quad (1)$$

where k denotes the target index, $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}} = [\theta_{\text{az}}^{\text{br}}, \theta_{\text{el}}^{\text{br}}]^\top$ is the known AoA from the BS to the RIS, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_{\text{az}}, \theta_{\text{el}}]^\top$ is the unknown AoD from the RIS to the target. In addition, α_k and α^{br} are complex channel gains, where α_k includes the effects of (i) two-way attenuation over the forward BS-RIS-target path and the backward target-RIS-BS path, and (ii) radar-cross-section (RCS) of the target [15]:

$$|\alpha_k|^2 = \frac{P_t G_b^2 G^2 F^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) F^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}}) d_x^2 d_y^2 \lambda^2 \sigma_{\text{RCS}}}{(4\pi)^5 d_{\text{br}}^4 d_k^4}. \quad (2)$$

Here, P_t is the transmit power, G_b is the BS antenna gain, G is the antenna power gain of an RIS patch, $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = (\cos \theta_{\text{el}})^{0.285}$ is the normalized RIS power radiation pattern [37, Eq. (3)], d_x and d_y represent the RIS element spacing along the local horizontal and vertical axes, respectively, λ denotes the carrier wavelength, σ_{RCS} is the target RCS, and, d_{br} and d_k denote the BS-RIS and RIS-target distances, respectively. Also in (1), $\tau = 2(d_{\text{br}} + d)/c$ and ν denote the round-trip delay and Doppler shift of the BS-RIS-target path, respectively, with c denoting the speed of propagation. The vector $\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times 1}$ denotes the array steering vector at the RIS, given as follows [38]:

$$[\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta})]_i = e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \cos \theta_{\text{el}} (\cos \theta_{\text{az}} p_{x,i} + \sin \theta_{\text{az}} p_{y,i})}, \quad (3)$$

where $p_{x,i}$ and $p_{y,i}$ denote the position of the i^{th} element in the horizontal and vertical axes of the RIS with respect to its center, respectively. The matrix $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_m = \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_m) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times N_{\text{RIS}}}$ is the RIS phase profile for the m^{th} symbol, containing RIS phase shifts $\boldsymbol{\omega}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times 1}$ on its diagonal. The frequency-domain steering vector $\mathbf{c}(\tau) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ as a function of delay τ is given by

$$\mathbf{c}(\tau) = [1, e^{-j2\pi\Delta_f\tau}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi(N-1)\Delta_f\tau}]^\top, \quad (4)$$

while the time-domain steering vector $\mathbf{d}(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ as a function of Doppler ν is expressed as

$$\mathbf{d}(\nu) = [1, e^{j2\pi T_s \nu}, \dots, e^{j2\pi(M-1)T_s \nu}]^\top. \quad (5)$$

Finally, $z_{n,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, N_0 N \Delta_f)$ is the additive complex Gaussian noise, with N_0 denoting the noise power spectral density (PSD) level.

To provide a more compact representation of (1), we define

$$\mathbf{b}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq \mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times 1}. \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, we obtain

$$y_{n,m} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k (\mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \boldsymbol{\omega}_m)^2 [\mathbf{c}(\tau_k)]_n [\mathbf{d}(\nu_k)]_m x_{n,m} + z_{n,m}. \quad (7)$$

We further introduce the collection of RIS phase profiles as

$$\mathbf{W} = [\boldsymbol{\omega}_0 \dots \boldsymbol{\omega}_{M-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times M}. \quad (8)$$

Using (8) and stacking over N subcarriers and M symbols, the model in (7) can be expressed in a compact matrix form as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X} \odot \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \mathbf{c}(\tau_k) (\mathbf{d}^\top(\nu_k) \odot \mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \mathbf{W}) + \mathbf{Z}, \quad (9)$$

$$\triangleq \sum_{k=1}^K \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}_k) + \mathbf{Z},$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ with $[\mathbf{Y}]_{n,m} = y_{n,m}$, $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ with $[\mathbf{X}]_{n,m} = x_{n,m}$, and $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is the additive noise matrix with $\text{vec}(\mathbf{Z}) \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, N_0 N \Delta_f \mathbf{I})$. For ease of exposition, we assume that all the symbols are 1, i.e., \mathbf{X} is an all-ones matrix. In this case, we discard the \mathbf{X} term and also define $\bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}_k)$, as shown in the last expression in (9).

C. Problem Formulation

Given the frequency/slow-time observation matrix \mathbf{Y} in (9), our goal is to detect the presence of multiple targets and estimate their delay, Doppler and azimuth-elevation angles. Due to the angle-Doppler coupling over the slow-time domain (manifested through the terms $\mathbf{d}^\top(\nu)$ and $\mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W}$), this poses a computationally complex problem. To tackle this challenge, in Sec. III we derive a generic GLRT detector and propose a tailor-made RIS phase profile design, along with a ML-based detector/estimator, to resolve the angle-Doppler coupling.

III. SINGLE-TARGET DETECTOR/ESTIMATOR AND RIS PROFILE DESIGN UNDER ANGLE-DOPPLER COUPLING

In this section, we study the case in which there exists only a single target in the scene. The proposed method for this case was first derived in [30], which is elaborated in more detail in this section. We first derive the GLRT detector for the sensing problem formulated in Sec. II-C, which leads to a high-complexity optimization. Then, we propose a three-step estimator that avoids high-dimensional parameter search in solving the GLRT, by exploiting the structure of a tailor-made RIS phase profile matrix.

A. GLRT Detector

In this case, (9) becomes

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^\top(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W}) + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (10)$$

To derive the GLRT detector, we re-cast (10) as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) + \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^\top(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W}), \quad (12)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\alpha, \tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}]^\top$ is the unknown parameter vector. Note that the RIS phase configuration matrix \mathbf{W} is under our control; hence, we can design \mathbf{W} according to the requirements for radar detection and estimation. The hypothesis testing problem for the model in (11) can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{Z}, & \text{under } \mathcal{H}_0 \\ \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) + \mathbf{Z}, & \text{under } \mathcal{H}_1 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

and the corresponding GLRT can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{Y}) = \frac{\max_{\boldsymbol{\eta}} p_1(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\eta})}{p_0(\mathbf{Y})} \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} \gamma \quad (14)$$

where γ is a threshold determined by a preset false alarm probability. In (14), the likelihood for the no-target case \mathcal{H}_0 is given by

$$p_0(\mathbf{Y}) = \frac{1}{(\pi\sigma^2)^{MN}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{Y}\|_F^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (15)$$

where $\sigma^2 = N_0 N \Delta_f$, while the likelihood for the target-present case \mathcal{H}_1 is given by

$$p_1(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \frac{1}{(\pi\sigma^2)^{MN}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{Y} - \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta})\|_F^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (16)$$

Substituting (15) and (16) into (14) and simplifying, we obtain the log-likelihood ratio up to an additive and multiplicative constant:

$$\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) = \min_{\eta} \|\mathbf{Y} - \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\eta)\|_F^2 - \|\mathbf{Y}\|_F^2. \quad (17)$$

In (17), the optimal channel gain can be estimated in closed-form as a function of delay, Doppler, and angle parameters [39]:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{\text{tr} \left((\mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}))^H \mathbf{Y} \right)}{\|\mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2}, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{h}(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq \mathbf{d}(\nu) \odot \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{b}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{b}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (19)$$

Plugging (18) into (17) yields, after removing irrelevant terms,

$$\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) = \quad (20)$$

$$\min_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}} \left\| \mathbf{Y} - \frac{\text{tr} \left((\mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}))^H \mathbf{Y} \right)}{\|\mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F} \mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right\|_F^2,$$

which can be simplified into (up to additive constants)

$$\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) = \max_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\tau) \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{h}^*(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right|^2}{\|\mathbf{h}(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\|^2}. \quad (21)$$

In general, no further simplification is possible, hence, a 4D search is needed to estimate delay, Doppler, and 2D angle.

B. ML-Based Estimator

To avoid the 4D search in (21), we harness the possibility of designing the RIS phase profile \mathbf{W} in (11). With the proposed design, the observation model can be expressed in a form that allows separation of delay and Doppler. Then, the delay-Doppler estimation is described, followed by 2D angle processing. Finally, a refinement of the estimates and target detection are presented.

1) *Repetitive RIS Phase Profile Design*: The RIS phase profile is adjusted at each symbol duration:

$$\mathbf{W} = [\omega_0 \cdots \omega_{M-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times M}, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \omega_0 \cdots \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \omega_{M-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times M}. \quad (23)$$

From (11), we can see that the time-domain part of the signal depends on $\mathbf{d}(\nu)$ and $\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W}$. We will try to eliminate the effects of coupling between $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and ν . To this end, we can repeat RIS profiles consecutively. In that case, we use L profiles and repeat each phase profile M/L times:

$$\underbrace{\omega_1 \omega_1 \cdots \omega_1}_{M/L \text{ times}} \underbrace{\omega_2 \omega_2 \cdots \omega_2}_{M/L \text{ times}} \cdots \underbrace{\omega_L \cdots \omega_L}_{M/L \text{ times}} \quad (24)$$

With this design, during each time interval (i.e., M/L times), the phase shift caused by the angles is constant since the RIS profile is constant. Hence, we can eliminate the coupling effect during each time interval.

2) *Observation Model with Repetitive RIS Phase Profiles*:

We again employ the signal model given in (11). However, to exploit the repetitive RIS phase profile on parameter estimation, we use another form of (11). For that reason, we define

$$\mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W}, \quad (25)$$

leading to

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot \mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})). \quad (26)$$

Using the RIS phase profile with repetition, we can rewrite $\mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ as

$$\mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \underbrace{(\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) [\omega_1 \cdots \omega_L])^2}_{\triangleq \mathbf{g}_L^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times L}} \otimes \mathbf{1}_{M/L}^T. \quad (27)$$

Therefore, we get

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) [\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot (\mathbf{g}_L^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{1}_{M/L}^T)] + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (28)$$

Next, we define

$$\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu) \triangleq [1 e^{j2\pi\nu T_s} \cdots e^{j2\pi\nu(M/L-1)T_s}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{M/L \times 1}$$

$$\mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \triangleq [1 e^{j2\pi\nu \frac{M}{L} T_s} \cdots e^{j2\pi\nu \frac{M}{L} (L-1) T_s}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1},$$

which allows us to write

$$\mathbf{d}(\nu) = \mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu). \quad (29)$$

Plugging (29) into (28) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} &= \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{1}_{M/L}) \odot (\mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu))]^T + \mathbf{Z}, \\ &= \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu)) \otimes (\mathbf{1}_{M/L} \odot \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu))]^T + \mathbf{Z}, \\ &= \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu)) \otimes (\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu))]^T + \mathbf{Z}. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

With this, we can now introduce $\boldsymbol{\beta} \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$, which will be a key to break down the 4D problem.

Based on the definition of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, we have that

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\boldsymbol{\beta} \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu))^T + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (31)$$

Considering (31), the observed signal \mathbf{Y} can be seen as the second mode unfolding matrix of a tensor $\mathcal{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times N \times M/L}$. For \mathcal{Y} , the l -th horizontal slice $[\mathcal{Y}]_{l, :, :}$ is expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y}_l = \beta_l \mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^T(\nu) + \mathbf{Z}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M/L} \quad (32)$$

where $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$.

3) *Delay-Doppler Estimation*: We estimate τ and ν from $\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_L$ by treating $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\beta_1, \dots, \beta_L]^T$ as nuisance parameters. Due to the independence of noise across l , the maximum-likelihood (ML) estimator is expressed as

$$\min_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\beta}} \sum_{l=1}^L \|\mathbf{Y}_l - \beta_l \mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^T(\nu)\|_F^2. \quad (33)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ can be obtained in closed form as a function of τ and ν , leading to

$$(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}) = \arg \max_{\tau, \nu} \sum_{l=1}^L \left| \mathbf{c}^H(\tau) \mathbf{Y}_l \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^*(\nu) \right|^2. \quad (34)$$

For a fast implementation of (34), we can first obtain a coarse estimate and then refine it via gradient ascent. To obtain the coarse estimate, we can evaluate the objective function in (34) by performing inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) over the frequency domain (second dimension) and fast Fourier transform (FFT) over the time domain (first dimension) for each \mathbf{Y}_l , and integrating non-coherently across l , which can be written as $\mathbf{Y}_{\tau, \nu} = \sum_{l=1}^L |\text{FFT}(\text{IFFT}(\mathbf{Y}_l, 2), 1)|^2$. Afterwards, we obtain the initial estimates for (τ, ν) as the argument that maximizes $\mathbf{Y}_{\tau, \nu}$. Note that since the range-Doppler map is quantized, one should perform fine tuning for improved approximation. Therefore, in our application, we first apply the aforementioned fast implementation and then perform gradient ascent over the objective function in (34) by employing the initial estimates.

4) *Angle Estimation*: Given delay-Doppler estimates $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu})$, we now wish to estimate azimuth and elevation angles $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_{az} \theta_{el}]^T$ from the observations (see (30), repeated RIS phase profiles). We find that

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\hat{\tau}) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\hat{\nu})) \otimes (\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}))]^T + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (35)$$

Again, α can be solved in closed form, so that the ML estimator becomes

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\hat{\tau}) \mathbf{Y} \left((\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\hat{\nu})) \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}) \right)^* \right|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|^2}, \quad (36)$$

which involves a 2D search over $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. At this search, a grid of points with 2-degree step size in azimuth-elevation is created. More specifically, the selected grid points are $\theta_{\text{az}} \leftarrow \{-90^\circ, -88^\circ, \dots, 90^\circ\}$ and $\theta_{\text{el}} \leftarrow \{0^\circ, 2^\circ, \dots, 90^\circ\}$. We choose the maximum point and perform gradient search by using the objective of (36).

5) *Refinement and Target Detection*: By using the estimates $\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, we initialize a 4D search to solve the maximization problem in (21), which is equivalent to

$$(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \arg \max_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\tau) \mathbf{Y} \left(\mathbf{g}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}(\nu) \right)^* \right|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{d}(\nu)\|^2}. \quad (37)$$

As will be discussed in the Section V, it is very likely for estimates to converge to a local maximum. To overcome such cases, we perform a grid search around the estimates obtained from (34) and (36). The grid points are only selected in Doppler domain, and are selected as $\mathbf{g}_{\text{dopp}} \leftarrow -r_{\text{dopp}}, -r_{\text{dopp}} + d_{\text{dopp}}, \dots, r_{\text{dopp}}$ where $r_{\text{dopp}} = 50, d_{\text{dopp}} = 0.5$. We evaluate the objective of (37) for each grid point for once and perform gradient search initialized with the maximizer point. The complete algorithm for the joint estimator is given in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 ML-Based Estimator (Single Target)

Input: \mathbf{Y}

Output: $(\hat{\tau}$ (m), $\hat{\nu}$ (m/s), $\hat{\theta}_{\text{az}}$ (deg), $\hat{\theta}_{\text{el}}$ (deg))

- 1: $\mathbf{Y}_{\tau, \nu} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}_{M \times N}$
 - 2: **for** $l = 1, \dots, L$ **do**
 - 3: $\mathbf{Y}_{\tau, \nu} \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}_{\tau, \nu} + |\text{FFT}(\text{IFFT}(\mathbf{Y}_l, 2), 1)|^2$
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: $(\tau_0, \nu_0) \leftarrow$ Values at maximizer indices of $\mathbf{Y}_{\tau, \nu}$
 - 6: $(\tilde{\tau}, \tilde{\nu}) \leftarrow$ Gradient ascent on (34), init: (τ_0, ν_0)
 - 7: $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0 \leftarrow$ Grid search over (36)
 - 8: $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \leftarrow$ Gradient ascent on (36), init: $\boldsymbol{\theta}_0$
 - 9: $\nu_0 \leftarrow$ Grid search over objective of (37) on Doppler domain, fixed $\tilde{\tau}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$
 - 10: $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \leftarrow$ Gradient ascent on (37), init: $(\tilde{\tau}, \nu_0, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$
-

After estimating the delay-Doppler-angle parameters as $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$, we plug them into the original GLRT expression in (37), yielding the following detection test

$$\frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\hat{\tau}) \mathbf{Y} \left(\mathbf{g}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \odot \mathbf{d}(\hat{\nu}) \right)^* \right|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \odot \mathbf{d}(\hat{\nu})\|^2} \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} \gamma. \quad (38)$$

IV. MULTI-TARGET DETECTOR/ESTIMATOR UNDER ANGLE-DOPPLER COUPLING

In this section, we use the single-target detector and estimator from Sec. III as a core sub-routine for an OMP-based estimator. We also derive a novel subspace-based method with lower complexity.

A. Model under Repetitive RIS Phase Profiles

For the multiple target case, the observed signal in (31) extends to a superposition of received signals from K targets, and the signal is expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{c}(\tau_k) (\boldsymbol{\beta}_k \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu_k))^T + \mathbf{Z}, \quad (39)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}_k = \alpha_k (\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu_k))$. Similar to the single target case, the goal is to detect the k -th target for $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, K-1\}$ and estimate its corresponding delay (τ_k), Doppler frequency (ν_k), and angles ($\boldsymbol{\theta}_k$). One particular challenge in such scenarios is the unknown number of targets (K). We propose two algorithms that address the detection and estimation problem while overcoming the challenge of an unknown number of targets.

B. OMP-Based Successive Algorithm

The proposed OMP-based successive algorithm extends the approach for the single target case. The algorithm treats the strongest target as the single target and considers the other targets' components as interference in each step, and try to detect and estimate the parameters of each target successively. There are similar applications available in the literature such as [36], [40], [41]. First, it performs the single-target ML-based algorithm which aims to estimate the strongest target's parameters and to calculate the single target GLRT accordingly. If the GLRT exceeds the specified threshold, the signal components of that target are extracted. Then, the same single target procedure is performed until the GLRT does not exceed the threshold. This procedure is explained in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 OMP-Based Estimator (Multiple Target)

Input: \mathbf{Y}

Output: $K, (\hat{\tau}_k$ (m), $\hat{\nu}_k$ (m/s), $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k$ (deg)), $\mathcal{L}_k^{\text{log}}, k = 1, \dots, K$

- 1: $k \leftarrow 0$
 - 2: proceed \leftarrow true
 - 3: **while** proceed = true **do**
 - 4: $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \leftarrow$ Algorithm 1(\mathbf{Y})
 - 5: $\mathcal{L}^{\text{log}}(\mathbf{Y}) \leftarrow$ objective of (38) evaluated at $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$
 - 6: **if** $\mathcal{L}^{\text{log}}(\mathbf{Y}) \geq \gamma$ **then**
 - 7: $k \leftarrow k + 1$
 - 8: $(\hat{\tau}_k, \hat{\nu}_k, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k) \leftarrow (\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$
 - 9: $\hat{\alpha}_k \leftarrow$ (18) evaluated with $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}), \mathbf{Y}$
 - 10: $\boldsymbol{\eta}_k \leftarrow (\hat{\alpha}_k, \hat{\tau}_k, \hat{\nu}_k, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k)$
 - 11: $\mathcal{L}_k^{\text{log}} \leftarrow \mathcal{L}^{\text{log}}(\mathbf{Y})$
 - 12: $\mathbf{Y} \leftarrow \mathbf{Y} - \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}_k)$
 - 13: **else**
 - 14: proceed \leftarrow false
 - 15: **end if**
 - 16: **end while**
 - 17: $K \leftarrow k$
-

In more detail, the algorithm performs the same single target procedure successively. Let us denote the residue of the observation at the k th iteration as $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{(k)}$. Initially, we set $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{(k)} = \mathbf{Y}$. First, it estimates the strongest target's range, Doppler and angle parameters $(\hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\nu}_1, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1)$ by using Algorithm 1 and its channel gain $\hat{\alpha}_1$ by (18) which creates the estimation vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1 = (\hat{\alpha}_1, \hat{\tau}_1, \hat{\nu}_1, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1)$. By using the estimates, GLRT is calculated and compared to a specified threshold. If it

exceeds this threshold, we detect a target corresponding to these estimates, and proceed to the next iteration over the new residue $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{(2)} = \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{(1)} - \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_1)$ to detect the second strongest target. The same procedure is applied until the GLRT does not exceed the threshold.

C. Subspace-Based Algorithm via Unitary ESPRIT

The OMP-based successive algorithm is accurate and can perform well under low-SNR conditions. However, its relatively high time complexity can limit its real-time application capabilities. Hence, we propose a subspace approach with a higher SNR threshold but reduced time complexity. Assuming an upper bound on the number of targets in the environment, the algorithm uses unitary ESPRIT to estimate the range and Doppler of the targets, followed by reconstructing associated matrices with range and Doppler. These matrices are then used to mitigate the influence of range and Doppler in the observed matrix. Finally, azimuth and elevation are extracted by solving an optimization problem.

1) *Range-Doppler Estimation:* In the estimation of range and Doppler parameters, we manipulate the observation data in such a way that it directly provides the input for the multiple snapshot unitary-ESPRIT method [42]. The output parameters of unitary-ESPRIT approach are automatically paired [42]. This subsection focuses on the manipulation of observational data to achieve this configuration. A brief description of the ESPRIT method is provided in Appendix A, which elucidates the underlying algorithmic principles involved.

Since the delays and Doppler shifts of the targets remain constant across all RIS phase profiles, we treat the RIS phase profiles as multiple snapshots of identical range-Doppler observations. We define \mathbf{y}_l as

$$\mathbf{y}_l = \text{vec}(\mathbf{Q}_{NM/L}^H \mathbf{Y}_l \mathbf{Q}_L^*), \quad (40)$$

where \mathbf{Y}_l , the observed signal for the l -th RIS profile, is given as

$$\mathbf{Y}_l = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{l,k} \mathbf{c}(\tau_k) \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^T(\nu_k) + \mathbf{Z}_l,$$

and $\mathbf{Q}_{NM/L}$ and \mathbf{Q}_L are arbitrary matrices with conjugate centrosymmetric rows. We construct the matrix \mathbf{Y}_s by stacking the vectors \mathbf{y}_l to form $\mathbf{Y}_s = [\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_L] \in \mathbb{C}^{NM/L \times L}$. The subsequent matrix,

$$\mathbf{Y}_{ri} = [\Re\{\mathbf{Y}_s\} \quad \Im\{\mathbf{Y}_s\}], \quad (41)$$

serves as the input for the standard multi-snapshot unitary ESPRIT algorithm, detailed further in Appendix A. Since the number of targets, K , is not known a-priori, we consider an upper bound, K_{ub} , on the number of targets and proceed to estimate range and Doppler parameters for each target. We have

$$\{(\tilde{\tau}_0, \tilde{\nu}_0), \dots, (\tilde{\tau}_{K_{ub}}, \tilde{\nu}_{K_{ub}})\} = \text{ESPRIT}(\mathbf{Y}_{ri}, K_{ub}). \quad (42)$$

2) *Angle Estimation:* We define the range and Doppler matrices, $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K_{ub}}$ and $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{C}^{M/L \times K_{ub}}$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{c}(\hat{\tau}_0) \quad \mathbf{c}(\hat{\tau}_1) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{c}(\hat{\tau}_{K_{ub}-1})],$$

$$\mathbf{D} = [\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}_0) \quad \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}_1) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}_{K_{ub}-1})].$$

Subsequently, we multiply \mathbf{Y}_l by \mathbf{C}^H and \mathbf{D}^* to mitigate the influence of range and Doppler parameters on the observed signal, given by

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_l = \text{diag}(\mathbf{C}^H \mathbf{Y}_l \mathbf{D}^*) \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times K_{ub}}. \quad (43)$$

For the k -th target, $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, K_{ub} - 1\}$, we construct $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_k = [[\hat{\beta}_0]_k, [\hat{\beta}_1]_k, \dots, [\hat{\beta}_{L-1}]_k]^T$, allowing the creation of

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{L,k} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_k \oslash \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}_k), \quad (44)$$

where \oslash denotes element-wise division. To estimate $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k$, we solve the following optimization problem

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \left\| \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{L,k} - \frac{\mathbf{g}_L^H(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \hat{\mathbf{g}}_{L,k}}{\|\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|^2} \right\|, \quad (45)$$

implemented through a two-stage algorithm. Initially, a grid search evaluates the loss function at predetermined grid points, incorporating azimuth and elevation angles. This is followed by a fine search stage where a local minimum is identified using a gradient descent algorithm, constrained by the grid search resolution.

3) *Refinement and Target Detection:* Upon parameter estimation, we refine the range and Doppler estimates through a 2D search, utilizing the maximization framework specified in (37) with fixed angle parameters $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. Supported by numerical experiments, the angle estimation meets the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB), allowing us to suffice with a low-complexity 2D search. We formulate the maximization problem follows:

$$(\hat{\Delta\tau}_k, \hat{\Delta\nu}_k) = \arg \max_{\Delta\tau, \Delta\nu} \mathcal{F}(\Delta\tau, \Delta\nu),$$

$$\text{subject to } -\frac{1}{4\Delta_f} \leq \Delta\tau \leq \frac{1}{4\Delta_f}, \quad (46)$$

$$-\frac{1}{4T_s} \leq \Delta\nu \leq \frac{1}{4T_s},$$

where

$$\mathcal{F}(\Delta\tau, \Delta\nu) = \frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\tilde{\tau}_k + \Delta\tau) \mathbf{Y} \left(\mathbf{g}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k) \oslash \mathbf{d}(\tilde{\nu}_k + \Delta\nu) \right)^* \right|^2}{\left\| \mathbf{g}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k) \oslash \mathbf{d}(\tilde{\nu}_k + \Delta\nu) \right\|^2},$$

$\hat{\tau}_k = \tilde{\tau}_k + \hat{\delta\tau}_k$, and $\hat{\nu}_k = \tilde{\nu}_k + \hat{\delta\nu}_k$. For each target estimate k , where $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, K_{ub} - 1\}$, the set $\{\hat{\tau}_k, \hat{\nu}_k, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k\}$ is estimated. Actual targets are distinguished from spurious detections using the GLRT, with genuine targets confirmed when their test values exceed a predefined threshold. The methodology is described in Algorithm 3.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Scenarios, Metrics, and Benchmarks

1) *Scenario and Parameters:* In the simulation setup, the center of the RIS is located at the origin, pointing towards the z-axis. Also, the BS is located 5 m away from the RIS with angle $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}} = (135^\circ, 80^\circ)$, which corresponds to $\mathbf{p}_{\text{BS}} = [-0.6139 \quad 0.6139 \quad 4.9240]^T$ m.

We define the BS antenna gain similar to phased array antennas to choose realistic parameters. Commonly, phased array antennas have isotropic elements. In our scenario, we consider the case where the BS has $N_{\text{BS}} = 64$ elements and has an antenna gain of $G_b = 10 \log_{10}(N_{\text{BS}}) = 18.06$ dB. We assume that the cyclic prefix is sufficiently long to avoid ISI. We generate our RIS phase profile to scan all the region behind the obstacle, which is a quarter sphere. In other words, we create equally spaced angular beams in the region of $\theta_{\text{az}} \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and $\theta_{\text{el}} \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ)$. In addition, $\lambda = 1.07$ cm and the number of RIS elements and the RIS element spacing are $N_{\text{RIS}} = 21 \times 21$ and $\lambda/4 = 2.7$ mm, respectively. The RIS elements are assumed to be isotropic, which results in $G = 0$ dB. The OFDM signal has $N = 256$ subcarriers with a

Algorithm 3 Subspace-Based Estimator (Multiple Target)

Input: \mathbf{Y} , K_{ub}
Output: K , $(\hat{\tau}_k$ (m), $\hat{\nu}_k$ (m/s), $\hat{\theta}_k$ (deg)), \mathcal{L}_k^{\log} , $k = 1, \dots, K$

```

1:  $\mathcal{Y} \leftarrow$  Fold  $\mathbf{Y}$  into a tensor
2: for  $l = 1, 2, \dots, L$  do
3:    $\mathbf{Y}_l \leftarrow$  the  $l$ -th horizontal slice of  $\mathcal{Y}$ 
4:    $\mathbf{y}_l \leftarrow$  Apply real-to-complex mapping (40)
5: end for
6:  $\mathbf{Y}_s \leftarrow$  Concatenate  $[\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_L]$ 
7:  $\mathbf{Y}_{ri} \leftarrow [\Re\{\mathbf{Y}_s\} \ \Im\{\mathbf{Y}_s\}]$ 
8:  $\{(\tilde{\tau}_0, \tilde{\nu}_0), \dots, (\tilde{\tau}_{K_{ub}}, \tilde{\nu}_{K_{ub}})\} \leftarrow$  Algorithm 4 ( $\mathbf{Y}_{ri}$ ,  $K_{ub}$ )
9:  $K \leftarrow 0$  Initialize count number of targets
10: for  $k = 0, 1, \dots, K_{ub} - 1$  do
11:    $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{L,k} \leftarrow$  Evaluate (44) on  $\hat{\beta}_k$  and  $\tilde{\nu}_k$ 
12:    $\hat{\theta}_{k,0} \leftarrow$  Grid search over (45)
13:    $\hat{\theta}_k \leftarrow$  Gradient descent on (45), init:  $(\hat{\theta}_{k,0})$ 
14:    $(\tilde{\tau}_k, \tilde{\nu}_k) \leftarrow$  Gradient ascent on (46), init:  $(\tilde{\tau}_k, \tilde{\nu}_k)$ 
15:    $\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) \leftarrow$  objective of (38) evaluated at  $(\tilde{\tau}_k, \tilde{\nu}_k, \hat{\theta}_k)$ 
16:   if  $\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) \geq \gamma$  then
17:      $(\hat{\tau}_k, \hat{\nu}_k, \hat{\theta}_k) \leftarrow (\tilde{\tau}_k, \tilde{\nu}_k, \hat{\theta}_k)$ 
18:      $\mathcal{L}_k^{\log} \leftarrow \mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y})$ 
19:      $K \leftarrow K + 1$ 
20:   end if
21: end for

```

spacing of $\Delta_f = 120$ kHz and $M = 1120$ symbols. The noise PSD level is $N_0 = -174$ dBm/Hz and the receiver noise figure is 8 dB. The transmit power is fixed to $P_t = 20$ dBm, unless otherwise is stated.

We consider several cases, including single and multiple target cases. We vary the values of some critical system parameters for different scenarios and perform the analyses described in the following.

2) *Performance Metrics:* For the multiple target case, both algorithms perform target detection and estimation. However, it is not known which detected target corresponds to which one of the targets. On the other hand, the algorithms can generate false alarms or miss some of the targets. For that reason, we need a target parameter assignment algorithm. Considering the aforementioned issues, Generalized Optimal Sub-Pattern Assignment (GOSPA) is a suitable candidate [43]. Let T and E be the sets of parameter vectors for the true targets and the detections, respectively. Each element in both sets is a vector of four estimated parameters $[\mathbf{p}, \nu]$, with \mathbf{p} denoting the Cartesian coordinates converted from the spherical coordinate parameters (τ, θ) . Now, denoting Ξ as the set of all possible assignment sets ξ , we have the GOSPA metric as

$$d_{\text{GOSPA},c}(T, E) = \min_{\xi \in \Xi} \sum_{(i,j) \in \xi} d_w(T_i, E_j) + \frac{c}{2}(\text{card}(T) + \text{card}(E) - 2\text{card}(\xi)),$$

where $\text{card}()$ denotes the cardinality, and $d_w(T_i, E_j)$ is the Doppler-weighted distance metric between the i th true target and j th detection, defined as

$$d_w([\mathbf{p}^T, \nu], [\hat{\mathbf{p}}^T, \hat{\nu}]) = \|\mathbf{p} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}\| + w|\nu - \hat{\nu}|.$$

Interpreting the metric, it can be seen that the only way to minimize the whole expression when $d_w(T_i, E_j) > c$ is that the detection must not be assigned to the true target so that the $2\text{card}(\xi)$ term decreases. Therefore, we can think of the

GOSPA metric as a weighted summation of distance, false alarm, and miss detection, and when the Doppler-weighted distance is more than c , we assign the detection as a false alarm.

3) *Benchmarks:* We employ the following benchmark schemes and metrics for comparison and evaluation purposes:

- Doppler ignorant (DI) detector/estimator: Algorithm 1 with the assumption of zero Doppler.
- Higher-order singular value decomposition (HOSVD): An SVD method employed in [29] for single target cases, which uses the same system model that is used in our work.
- Cramér-Rao bound (CRB): We derive the CRB for each parameter dimension and compare it with the root mean-squared error (RMSE) of the proposed algorithms (Algorithm 1, Algorithm 2 and Algorithm 3) and the considered benchmark schemes.

DI estimation scheme is employed to analyze the effects of Doppler estimation on target detection performance. In the DI approach, we apply an IFFT to the frequency domain to generate a range profile for each repetition interval. To enhance estimation accuracy, we perform non-coherent integration over the time domain for each range bin and select the largest peak as the range estimate. To further improve the range estimation, we apply gradient ascent over the objective function in (34), while keeping the Doppler component fixed at zero. Once the range and Doppler values are determined, we perform a search over the entire azimuth-elevation domain using a grid with 2-degree step sizes in both azimuth and elevation. The point with the maximum value is selected, and gradient ascent is applied again to refine the angle estimates, following the objective function in (36). With these estimates in hand, and still fixing Doppler at zero, we perform a final gradient ascent over the objective function in (38), starting from the initial estimates to further fine-tune the solution.

In addition to the DI method, we evaluate the performance of the HOSVD method, as proposed in [29], by implementing it in single-target scenarios. The HOSVD method is then compared against the developed techniques and the DI method. It is important to note that due to the lack of a pairing strategy in the HOSVD method, it is not implemented as a benchmark in multi-target scenarios, where accurate target pairing across multiple dimensions is crucial for performance evaluation.

In all considered cases, we run 2000 Monte-Carlo tests for each parameter set. We perform 4D ML estimation using OMP, subspace and for some cases, DI methods, and calculate the GLRT using these estimates. We calculate the RMSE based on Monte-Carlo trials and compare it with the CRB. To study detection performance, we perform thresholding over GLRT values. Finally, we derive the CRB to assess the efficiency of the estimators.

B. Results and Discussion

We consider three scenarios with the first one being performance analysis for different target distances. In this analysis, our aim is to evaluate the estimation performance for different approaches and analyze the detection performance by checking the GLRT values. The second scenario investigates the estimation performance for varying coverage areas. In tracking scenarios, it is possible to focus on smaller regions where the

target can be present. In that sense, we analyze the performance of our proposed methods in tracking scenarios. Lastly, we consider a two-target case with a weak target and a strong target present in the scanned region. We analyse detection and estimation performances of the OMP and the subspace method.

Note that due to the periodicity with respect to the phases corresponding to the unknown target parameters and the limited search space, the values of the estimates are constrained. In particular, the range is limited to $[0, 1250]$ m, the Doppler velocity is limited to $[-321.4, 321.4]$ m/s, the azimuth is limited to $[-180, 180]$ degrees, and the elevation is limited to $[0, 90]$ degrees.

1) *Scenario 1: Single Target vs. Distance:* In this scenario, we analyse the performance of the algorithms for the single target case. We place a target with 0.5 m^2 RCS at the direction of $(30, 50)$ degrees of the RIS. We vary the distance of the target from the RIS and compare the performance of the subspace, OMP, HOSVD, and DI methods.

The RMSEs of the target parameters are presented in Figs. 2–5. In Fig. 2, all four algorithms exhibit the waterfall behavior. Specifically, the subspace method diverges from the CRLB earlier than the OMP algorithm, while the DI method exhibits large gap from the CRLB but with similarity to OMP, showing step-like behavior at the same region. The earlier divergence of the subspace method suggests that it requires a higher SNR than OMP to converge to the CRLB, which can be attributed to the suboptimal nature of the subspace method. Meanwhile, large gap to CRLB is observed in DI is expected since DI essentially operates similarly to OMP but assumes a zero Doppler shift. Additionally, the HOSVD method achieves performance between OMP and the subspace method in terms of range estimation.

In Fig. 3, the Doppler error component for the DI method remains constant, as DI assumes zero Doppler. When comparing the subspace and OMP methods, a similar behavior to that in Fig. 2 is observed, where both methods exhibit the waterfall effect. However, HOSVD does not converge to the CRLB. This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that HOSVD estimates Doppler independently of the other parameters, while the subspace and OMP methods jointly estimate range and Doppler, leading to better convergence. For larger distances, the subspace, HOSVD, and OMP methods have higher RMSE values than DI. This is expected since DI has a fixed error, whereas the other methods are more susceptible to low SNR, which can result in larger errors.

In Fig. 4, the same waterfall effect seen in Fig. 2 is observed. For shorter distances, the RMSE of HOSVD diverges from the CRLB. This can be attributed to the objective function for angle estimation (Eq. (28) in [29]) not being an unbiased estimator, leading to a bias error of approximately 0.16 degrees in low-noise scenarios, which manifests as a constant RMSE. Fig. 5 exhibits a behavior similar to that in Figs. 2 and 4.

2) *Scenario 2: Single Target in Tracking Scenario:* In this case, we assume that the angular region is known to some extent. Hence, we change the percentage of the scanned region to see the effect of focusing the beams towards the target. Zero percent means that the beam is fixed to the center of the search region, which is $(0, 45)$ degrees of az-el angles, and 100 percent represents the total coverage. Decreasing the percentage is expected to increase the integrated SNR across all beams since there are more beams illuminating the target.

Fig. 2. RMSE of range estimation of the target for subspace and OMP methods with respect to distance between RIS and the target.

Fig. 3. RMSE of Doppler estimation of the target for subspace and OMP methods with respect to distance between RIS and the target.

Fig. 4. RMSE of azimuth estimation of the target for subspace and OMP methods with respect to distance between RIS and the target.

Fig. 5. RMSE of elevation estimation of the target for subspace and OMP methods with respect to distance between RIS and the target.

We evaluate the performance of the algorithms versus the

percent of the coverage of the angular region. The target with 0.5 m^2 RCS is located at $(0, 45)$ degrees of az-el angles to and 1 m away from the RIS.

The results are given in Figs. 6–8. It is seen that narrowing the angle coverage decreases CRLBs and RMSEs as a result of an SNR increase since the beams are more focused on the target. We also observe that the RMSEs of range, Doppler and angle estimation obtained by both of the proposed algorithms converge to the CRLB for almost all the coverage percentages under consideration. This success results from the fact that SNR is sufficient for the considered tracking scenario with a close-by target unlike the search scenario in Sec. V-B1.

Fig. 6. RMSE of range estimation for different coverage areas.

Fig. 7. RMSE of Doppler estimation for different coverage areas.

3) *Scenario 3: Strong/Weak Targets*: In this scenario, we consider two targets: one target is strong (closer to the RIS with a high RCS), while the other is weaker. The targets are distinguishable across all dimensions. The strong target, with an RCS of 0.7 m^2 , is located 7 meters away from the RIS at the azimuth-elevation angles of $(30^\circ, 50^\circ)$ and has a velocity vector of $[15, 0, 15]$, resulting in a Doppler velocity of -19.8 m/s . Meanwhile, the weaker target, with an RCS of 0.3 m^2 , is located 10 meters away at the azimuth-elevation angles of $(-30^\circ, 60^\circ)$, with a velocity vector of $[-15, 0, -15]$, yielding a Doppler velocity of 19.5 m/s . Target detection and parameter estimation are performed using the subspace, OMP, and DI methods under the same conditions.

The subspace method estimates the parameters for a predefined maximum number of targets and returns them along with their GLRT values. Detection is then performed by applying a threshold to these GLRT values. In contrast, the OMP and DI methods estimate the parameters, compute their GLRT, and iteratively perform detection by thresholding until the

Fig. 8. RMSE of azimuth and elevation estimation for different coverage areas.

GLRT value falls below the threshold. Fig. 9 illustrates the target detection performance, while Figs. 10–12 depict the parameter estimation performance. As shown in Fig. 9, OMP demonstrates superior detection performance compared to the subspace and DI methods, with DI generally exhibiting the poorest performance. The primary limitation of the subspace method, as with the single-target case, is its need for higher SNR to detect the targets. This is partly due to the fact that the subspace method estimates the maximum number of targets, leading to inaccurate parameter estimation for the weaker target, which can result in its components being divided across several targets, thereby degrading detection performance. In contrast, DI performs the worst across most conditions, except for the weak target between 30 dBm and 37.5 dBm transmit power. The weaker performance for the strong target is expected, as the Doppler error affects the estimation of other parameters, resulting in a lower GLRT. Additionally, DI does not exhibit a monotonic trend due to residuals left from the first target component.

Range estimation performance is illustrated in Fig. 10. Both the subspace and OMP methods demonstrate convergence to the CRLB, whereas DI exhibits large gap between RMSE and CRLB due to the zero-Doppler assumption. Notably, the RMSE calculations only begin at points where the probability of detection is non-zero, as RMSEs cannot be calculated for undetected targets. Similarly, Fig. 11 shows the Doppler estimation performance. For DI, the error remains constant due to the zero-Doppler assumption, while both the subspace and OMP methods exhibit the waterfall effect. However, their behavior differs: the subspace method fails to converge to the CRLB due to its suboptimality, while the OMP method suffers from high estimation errors below 17.5 dBm and 27.5 dBm transmit power, leading to undetected targets in these regions.

The azimuth estimation performance, depicted in Fig. 12, demonstrates improved convergence compared to Doppler estimation. The OMP method is not impacted by Doppler estimations that are diverging from the CRLB since the Doppler errors remain moderate. Initially, DI converges toward the CRLB but diverges at higher transmit powers, consistent with the similarities between the OMP and DI methods. When their Doppler RMSEs are comparable, the errors in other

Fig. 9. Probability of detection of strong and weak targets for subspace and OMP methods with respect to transmit power.

Fig. 10. RMSE of range estimation of strong and weak targets for subspace and OMP methods with respect to transmit power.

parameters are also similar. However, as the transmit power increases, OMP achieves lower Doppler RMSE, while the Doppler RMSE of DI remains constant. As a result, the azimuth RMSE of OMP continues to track the CRLB, whereas DI diverges. The subspace method exhibits a similar trend but with some unexpected behaviors. A drop in RMSE at lower transmit powers is due to the GOSPA metric assigning large-error estimates as false alarms, leaving only small-error estimates assigned to the target. This results in the drop seen at low transmit powers. A similar phenomenon occurs in the tail of the RMSE curve for the weaker target at 40 dBm, where new points are assigned. The elevation errors follow a similar trend to the azimuth errors shown in Fig. 12.

C. Time Complexity Analysis

As previously mentioned, the subspace method is developed as a low-complexity solution. Consequently, it is expected to provide faster results despite some performance degradation. To quantify this trade-off in terms of time complexity, we conduct 2000 Monte-Carlo trials for both single and multiple target cases to evaluate the computational efficiency of the proposed methods. These simulations allow us to observe and compare the time complexities under various conditions, particularly between the subspace and OMP methods.

Fig. 11. RMSE of Doppler estimation of strong and weak targets for subspace and OMP methods with respect to transmit power.

Fig. 12. RMSE of azimuth estimation of strong and weak targets for subspace and OMP methods with respect to transmit power.

For these tests, we report the mean and standard deviation (STD) of the time consumed during one Monte-Carlo trial. The trials are executed on two systems: a laptop equipped with an Intel i7-9750H processor and a server running an Intel Xeon W5-3423 processor. The laptop's processor supports 12 threads, while the server can handle 24 threads. These hardware setups also enable us to assess the impact of processor architecture and threading capabilities on the computational performance of the algorithms.

In the single target case, we utilize Scenario 1, where the time consumption remains relatively consistent across different range values. Therefore, we combine the results for all range values and present the aggregate timing data in Table I. From these results, it is evident that the subspace method is approximately 20 times faster than the OMP method. Additionally, increasing the number of processor cores more than doubles the speed of both algorithms. However, it is important to note that the exact time consumption varies due to the differences in processor architectures between the laptop and the server. It is also noted that DI and HOSVD have comparable time complexity to OMP.

For the multiple target case, we consider Scenario 3, which involves two distinct targets. In this instance, we focus on the region where both targets are successfully detected. The time consumption for this case is presented in Table II. When

TABLE I
EXECUTION TIME OF A MONTE-CARLO TRIAL IN SINGLE TARGET CASE.

Method/# of cores	12	24
Subspace	Mean: 9.39×10^{-2} s Std: 1.22×10^{-4} s	Mean: 4.69×10^{-4} s Std: 4.03×10^{-3} s
OMP	Mean: 2.48×10^0 s Std: 1.92×10^{-1} s	Mean: 7.75×10^{-1} s Std: 7.54×10^{-4} s
DI	Mean: 1.87×10^0 s Std: 2.14×10^{-1} s	Mean: 4.83×10^{-1} s Std: 2.11×10^{-2} s
HOSVD	Mean: 5.92×10^{-1} s Std: 7.19×10^{-2} s	Mean: 2.20×10^{-1} s Std: 1.16×10^{-2} s

comparing the multiple target case to the single target case, it is apparent that the time consumption of the OMP method nearly doubles. This behavior is expected given the successive nature of the OMP method; doubling the number of targets effectively doubles the time required, as the same procedure is applied to each target individually. In contrast, the subspace method exhibits only a modest increase in time complexity when the number of targets is increased. Also, DI has similar time complexity to OMP, as expected.

From these results, we can conclude that the subspace method exhibits significantly lower computational complexity compared to the OMP method. Furthermore, while increasing the number of targets leads to a near-linear increase in time complexity for the OMP method, the subspace method shows only a minimal rise in computation time. This makes the subspace method a more efficient choice, especially in scenarios involving multiple targets, where the relative computational savings become even more pronounced.

TABLE II
EXECUTION TIME OF A MONTE-CARLO TRIAL IN TWO-TARGET CASE.

Method/# of cores	12	24
Subspace	Mean: 1.34×10^{-1} s Std: 1.07×10^{-2} s	Mean: 7.60×10^{-2} s Std: 5.25×10^0 s
OMP	Mean: 4.78×10^0 s Std: 1.82×10^{-1} s	Mean: 1.54×10^0 s Std: 3.72×10^{-2} s
DI	Mean: 4.27×10^0 s Std: 1.60×10^{-1} s	Mean: 1.11×10^0 s Std: 2.77×10^{-2} s

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we addressed the time-domain coupling of Doppler and angle for RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing. To resolve the coupling, we designed repetitive RIS phase profiles, and derived an ML-based target parameter estimator that estimates delay, Doppler, and angles. We also presented the GLRT for target detection. In addition, as a low-complexity alternative, we developed a novel subspace method that uses tensors to separate the parameter spaces. We generated a simulation environment for several single-target scenarios to analyze the estimation performance and a multiple-target scenario for investigating both detection and estimation performance. We constructed the RMSE figures to show that, via the proposed approaches, the RMSE converges to the CRB for sufficiently large SNRs, and the OMP method requires less power than the subspace method for accurate parameter estimation. In addition, the detection performance was depicted to show that with higher transmit powers, we can accurately detect the target's presence by having a reasonable false alarm rate.

APPENDIX A ESPRIT FOR RANGE-DOPPLER DERIVATION

Revisiting the ESPRIT algorithm ensures the methodology of this paper is self-contained. The in-depth analysis and derivation of the algorithm are not included. Using \mathbf{Y}_{ri} in (41) as the input for the ESPRIT algorithm, we first decompose the matrix using SVD on the matrix. We then select the left eigenvectors, $\mathbf{U}_s \in \mathbb{C}^{2NM/L \times K_{ub}}$, corresponding to the K_{ub} largest eigenvalues. We obtain ([42], eq. (38) and (40))

$$\mathbf{K}_{\tau_1} \mathbf{U}_s \mathbf{\Psi}_\tau = \mathbf{K}_{\tau_2} \mathbf{U}_s \quad (47)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\nu_1} \mathbf{U}_s \mathbf{\Psi}_\nu = \mathbf{K}_{\nu_2} \mathbf{U}_s. \quad (48)$$

where

$$\mathbf{K}_{\tau_1} = \mathbf{I}_{M/L} \otimes \Re \{ \mathbf{Q}_{N-1}^H \mathbf{J}_{N-1} \mathbf{Q}_N \}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\tau_2} = \mathbf{I}_{M/L} \otimes \Im \{ \mathbf{Q}_{N-1}^H \mathbf{J}_{N-1} \mathbf{Q}_N \}$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\nu_1} = \Re \{ \mathbf{Q}_{M/L-1}^H \mathbf{J}_{M/L-1} \mathbf{Q}_{M/L} \} \otimes \mathbf{I}_N$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\nu_2} = \Im \{ \mathbf{Q}_{M/L-1}^H \mathbf{J}_{M/L-1} \mathbf{Q}_{M/L} \} \otimes \mathbf{I}_N$$

and for any integer $P > 2$, $\mathbf{J}_P = [\mathbf{0}_{P-1,1} \quad \mathbf{I}_{P-1}]$. Moreover, $\mathbf{\Psi}_\tau = (\mathbf{\Xi}^{-1} \mathbf{\Omega}_\tau \mathbf{\Xi})$ ([42], eq. (42)) and $\mathbf{\Psi}_\nu = (\mathbf{\Xi}^{-1} \mathbf{\Omega}_\nu \mathbf{\Xi})$ ([42], eq. (43)) are the solutions to equations (47) and (48), respectively. To achieve automatic pairing between range and Doppler estimates, we calculate the eigenvalue matrix $\mathbf{\Omega}$ associated with matrix $\mathbf{\Psi}_\tau + 1j\mathbf{\Psi}_\nu$. The range and Doppler estimates are then determined based on these eigenvalues. Specifically [42],

$$\hat{\tau}_k = -\frac{1}{\pi \Delta_f} \arctan([\Re\{\mathbf{\Omega}\}]_{k,k}) \quad (49)$$

$$\hat{\nu}_k = -\frac{1}{\pi T_s} \arctan([\Im\{\mathbf{\Omega}\}]_{k,k}), \quad (50)$$

for $k = 1, \dots, K$. Algorithm 4 summarizes ESPRIT.

Algorithm 4 ESPRIT Algorithm

Input: \mathbf{Y}_{ri} , K_{ub}

Output: $(\tilde{\tau}_k \text{ (m)}, \tilde{\nu}_k \text{ (m/s)}), k = 1, \dots, K_{ub}$

- 1: $\mathbf{U}_s \leftarrow$ SVD of \mathbf{Y}_{ri}
- 2: $(\mathbf{\Psi}_\tau, \mathbf{\Psi}_\nu) \leftarrow$ Solve (47) and (48)
- 3: $\mathbf{\Omega} \leftarrow$ Eigenvalues of $\mathbf{\Psi}_\tau + 1j\mathbf{\Psi}_\nu$
- 4: $\{(\tilde{\tau}_0, \tilde{\nu}_0), \dots, (\tilde{\tau}_{K_{ub}}, \tilde{\nu}_{K_{ub}})\} \leftarrow$ Calculate (49) and (50)

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